

An LLM Framework for Long-form Video Retrieval and Audio-Visual Question Answering Using Qwen2/2.5

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Abstract

This paper presents our approach to tackle the tasks of Known Item Search (KIS) and Video Question Answering (Video QA) by combining state-of-the-art LLMs and cross-modal video retrieval methods. Regarding the KIS task, we analyze and decompose input queries into meaningful and easy-to-handle single-sentence sub-queries using an LLM, and for each sub-query we retrieve the relevant video shots using a learnable cross-modal network. Subsequently, we employ an aggregation module to combine the results of all the sub-queries into a single ranked list of retrieved shots. Regarding the Video QA task, following the retrieval of relevant videos using the aforementioned approach, we propose a methodology that is suitable for audio-visual question answering on long videos. Specifically, we adopt a caption-based LLM framework, which we augment with an audio processing component. To make this efficiently applicable on long videos, we design a keyword-based frame and audio segment selection mechanism, utilizing multimodal LLMs for filtering. This enables our framework to focus on the salient segments of the video. In addition, we implement an LLM-based self-feedback mechanism to check whether the candidate responses answer the original question, which makes our Video QA approach more robust to imperfect retrieval results.

1. Introduction

Searching for specific, known video items in large archives and answering questions in natural language about the retrieved videos is a significant challenge in the fields of com-

puter vision and multimedia research. Known-item search (KIS) involves identifying a unique video clip based on a textual description provided by the user, while automatic video question answering (Video QA) demands a deep understanding of both audio-visual and textual modalities to generate meaningful responses. These tasks are naturally complex, as even human experts struggle with them in interactive retrieval scenarios such as the Video Browser Showdown (VBS) [19] competition, where expert analysts need to search through large video datasets to find specific video moments.

The challenges associated with these tasks arise from several factors. First, visual content is complex, making it difficult to establish a direct match between a user query and an appropriate video segment. Second, the need to understand temporal dependencies and multi-modal relationships requires advanced reasoning skills that exceed simple visual similarity matching. Third, the variability in language used in user queries demands strong natural language understanding, as even minor differences in phrasing can greatly affect retrieval and reasoning performance. These factors contribute to the performance gap observed between state-of-the-art automated systems and human retrieval experts.

In this paper, we propose a novel approach to addressing these challenges, combining the power of recent text-based video retrieval models with the reasoning capabilities of multimodal LLMs [4] [38]. We utilize an LLM to break down the textual descriptions of the original user-generated query, in order to facilitate bridging the semantic gap between the video and text modalities. We subsequently apply a well-performing text-based video retrieval pipeline

to identify candidate video shots, based on the identified sub-queries. Moreover, we introduce a simple aggregation approach for aggregating the retrieved video shots for the multiple sub-queries. For video question answering, we again leverage the reasoning capabilities of LLMs. We adopt a caption-based Video QA framework and extend it to also include audio analysis. Additionally, we implement a keyword-based mechanism for selecting relevant frames and audio segments, allowing our framework to focus on the most salient portions of the long-form video. Finally, we design an LLM-based self-feedback component to rank the generated answers to the input Video QA query.

The contributions of this work are as follows:

- We propose a novel hybrid framework for known-item search and video question answering that combines text-based retrieval with multimodal LLM reasoning.
- We introduce an LLM-guided query decomposition technique to better align textual queries with video content.
- We design an aggregation mechanism that combines retrieval results from sub-queries to improve shot relevance.
- We extend a caption-based Video QA approach with audio-based analysis and a keyword-driven selection of salient video/audio segments.
- We implement a self-feedback module using LLMs to automatically rank candidate answers in Video QA.

2. Related work

2.1. Video search

With the advent of deep learning, research in text-based video search has evolved considerably. Recent models leverage large-scale pre-trained vision–language representations to project both video content and natural language queries into a common embedding space. Notable examples include CLIP-based methods such as CLIP4Clip [20] and Frozen in Time [5], which have demonstrated robust performance by effectively aligning semantic features across modalities. These approaches have been further extended by works that tackle challenges specific to videos containing multiple distinct events. For instance, multi-event video–text retrieval frameworks segment queries into event-specific units, thereby enhancing retrieval accuracy [41]. Additional lines of research focus on multi-query retrieval strategies that mitigate issues related to noisy annotations and sparse supervision, enabling more reliable matching between complex textual queries and video content [34]. Furthermore, initiatives such as the Text Retrieval Conference (TREC) workshop series, conducted by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), have significantly enhanced our understanding of text-to-video retrieval. In particular, the Video Browser Showdown (VBS) [19] challenge addresses these issues through an interactive format, while the TREC Ad-hoc Video Search (AVS) Task

[2] focuses on the retrieval of videos based on shorter textual descriptions. In parallel to these innovations, recent work [6] has introduced techniques for further improving retrieval effectiveness. By leveraging a pre-constructed set of representative “background” queries to recalibrate similarity scores, this method effectively mitigates the hubness problem - whereby a few gallery items dominate the nearest neighbor lists in high-dimensional embedding spaces - thus enhancing the matching of complex natural language queries to video content. Despite these advances, challenges remain in addressing intricate temporal dynamics and semantic nuances inherent in natural language descriptions. Recent surveys [43] highlight that while deep learning frameworks have significantly narrowed the semantic gap, further research is needed to handle the rich variability and complexity of real-world video content.

2.2. Video question answering

The standard state-of-the-art approach for the Video Question Answering (Video QA) task involves training a multimodal LLM (e.g. video models [33] [1] [18] [21] [42] [16] or audio-visual models [28] [12]) on a large-scale video training corpus. Multimodal LLMs combine modality-specific encoders or adapters with a Large Language Model. The main challenges of this approach are the quality and quantity of the training data, the compute requirements for training, and, more importantly, for tasks that involve long videos, the problem of scaling during inference. In order to address these challenges, many other works design training-free pipelines, utilizing pre-trained LLMs as pipeline components. For example, LLoVi [40] proposes a simple pipeline where the video is converted to a sequence of captions and a text-only LLM is used to process the captions and answer the question. Q-ViD [22] proposes extracting question-aware captions from the video. Vamos [29] and VidCtx [11] propose utilizing both modalities (i.e. captions and frames) for downstream tasks. LangRepo [13] introduces a textual memory component for long-range video modeling. However, a significant research question is how to integrate additional modalities, such as audio, in these frameworks. Following the above works, we adopt the caption-based architecture as the foundation for our method, which we augment with an audio processing component, in order to be able to efficiently process long audio-visual signals.

In a different direction, several works investigate how to improve the frame sampling operation, in order to enable the model to focus on the salient parts of the video. Early works, before the wide-spread usage of LLMs, such as MIST [9], FineCo [35] and Locate-before-Answering [25], design custom temporal localization modules to guide the sampling process. In contrast, SeViLa [39] leverages a pre-trained multimodal LLM to filter the relevant frames be-

Figure 1. An overview of the proposed pipelines for tackling the KIS and Video QA tasks.

fore generating an answer. LVNet [24] implements a stage-wise filtering pipeline with LLMs, utilizing keywords for coarse-grained filtering. VideoTree [36] implements a hierarchical LLM-guided sampling process. Finally, a promising research direction is the use of LLM agents [32] to guide the sampling process. Inspired by these works, we introduce an LLM-based frame sampling component, which we also extend to handle audio signals.

3. Approach

3.1. Overview

The overall structure of our methods for addressing the KIS and Video QA tasks is illustrated in Fig. 1. Regarding the KIS task, the proposed approach comprises three discrete stages. In Stage 1 (top-left part of Fig. 1), the input query is first classified as pertaining to either a single or multiple video shots and is then segmented into a concise list of descriptive sentences (sub-queries) using a designated LLM. In Stage 2 (detailed in Fig. 2), these sub-queries are processed through a Retrieval Module (RM). This aggregates the relevance scores calculated using several pre-trained vision-language models, subsequently fuses them via a Learnable Weighting Network (LWN), and fi-

nally normalizes them against background queries to further improve the similarity-based ranking of relevant shots. Finally, Stage 3 aggregates the ranked lists of relevant shots retrieved for each sub-query, resulting in a final ranked list of retrieved video shots. The LLM prompts that we utilize for the KIS task are listed in Tab. 1.

For Video Question Answering, we first split the query into two parts: the retrieval query and the Video QA question. Then, we retrieve the most relevant videos based on the retrieval query using the approach sketched above for the KIS task, and subsequently attempt to answer the given question with a caption-based LLM framework for Video QA. We extend this framework for audio understanding and also implement a keyword-based frame and audio segment selection component, utilizing multimodal LLMs. Finally, we leverage an LLM to order the candidate responses based on whether the responses answer the original question. In the right part of Figure Fig. 1 we present a diagram of our proposed VQA pipeline and in Tab. 2 we provide the corresponding list of LLM prompts that we utilize.

3.2. Known-Item Search approach

Stage 1 – Query Handling The initial phase of our methodology is dedicated to determining whether the input

LLM	Prompt
LLM_{split}	Does the following text contains phrases like “The next shot”, “The following shot”, “The second shot shows” or any phrases indicating that we talk about more than one shot? Answer “Yes” or “No”. Text: $\langle Query \rangle$
LLM_{shots}	Analyze the following video description and break it into its individual shots. Look for explicit cues such as “the first one shows”, “the next”, “following shot”, or similar phrases that indicate a change in camera take. For each distinct shot, list it using a sequential label (Shot A, Shot B, etc.). Provide only the final list as your answer. Text: $\langle Query \rangle$
$LLM_{sentences}$	Divide the following video description into a series of short, clear sentences where each sentence captures one distinct visual detail. These sentences will be used iteratively in a text-to-video retrieval system: first, the system will retrieve videos based on the first sentence, then it will refine the search using the second sentence, and so on. Please output a numbered list of sentences that preserve the order and meaning of the original description. Text: $\langle Query \rangle$

Table 1. LLM prompts for Known Item Search

LLM	Prompt
$LLM_{preprocess}$	You are given a text segment that contains both descriptive information about a specific video and a question related to that video. Your task is to divide this text into two clearly defined parts: 1. Video Identification Information - Extract and consolidate all details that uniquely describe or help locate the video. This includes visual details, geographic features, temporal information (e.g. year, date), metadata, and any context that identifies the video. 2. Reformulated Question: - Rewrite the question so that it is fully self-contained. - Integrate only the essential context directly needed to answer the question. - Ensure the question includes only the minimal context that is directly relevant to answering it. General Rules: - Clearly separate the two parts using labels such as “Video Identification Information” and “Reformulated Question”. The “Video Identification Information” should include all descriptive details, while the “Reformulated Question” should incorporate only the key details that indicate where the answer can be found. Input: $\langle Query \rangle$
$LLM_{keywords}$	What keywords should I search for in order to answer the following question: $\langle Question \rangle$ Answer with a comma-separated list of 5 keywords.
$LLM_{videofilter}$	Is this frame relevant to any of the following keywords: $\langle Keywords \rangle$? Answer with yes or no.
$LLM_{audiofilter}$	Is this audio relevant to any of the following keywords: $\langle Keywords \rangle$? Answer with yes or no.
$LLM_{caption}$	Provide a description of the video frame in 20 words or less.
$LLM_{transcribe}$	Transcribe the audio. Respond with the contents only.
LLM_{qa}	Captions: $\langle Captions \rangle$ Subtitles: $\langle Subtitles \rangle$ Considering the video frame captions and audio subtitles, answer the following question: $\langle Question \rangle$
$LLM_{feedback}$	Does the following text answer the question?. Answer with yes or no. Question: $\langle Question \rangle$ Text: $\langle Answer \rangle$

Table 2. LLM prompts for Video Question Answering

query refers to a single shot or multiple shots. For this purpose, we utilize LLM_{split} prompt, which provides a binary classification between two cases:

Case 1: Multiple Shots When the input query indicates multiple shots, LLM_{shots} prompt is employed to partition the query into distinct text segments, each corresponding to an individual shot. This segmentation yields a collection of text segments. Subsequently, $LLM_{sentences}$ is applied to each segment, resulting in a series of sentences (sub-queries) per shot.

Case 2: Single Shot In instances where the input query pertains to a single shot, $LLM_{sentences}$ is directly applied to decompose the query into a list of concise, descriptive sentences.

Stage 2 – Text-to-Video Retrieval The second phase of our pipeline involves the retrieval process. At this stage, the list of sentences generated in Stage 1 is used to compute a relevance score for each sentence relative to the shots within our video collection (in our case, the V3C1 [27] dataset), thereby producing a relevant-shot list for each sentence. This is accomplished by passing the sentences through the Retrieval Module (RM), as depicted in Fig. 2.

To enhance robustness, our approach incorporates five distinct vision-language model families, each with its own pre-trained models. For each shot, we sample a sequence of frames. Then, for each pre-trained model, we utilize a Similarity Module (SM). This module extracts visual features from each frame and averages them to create a single representative feature vector for the shot. In parallel, it extracts the corresponding textual feature and computes a similarity score between the shot-level feature vector and the text feature vector via cosine similarity. The scores derived from the SMs, within each model family, are summed to produce a single similarity value per model family. Consequently, this procedure yields five similarity values for each shot.

These values are integrated using a Learnable Weighting Network (LWN)[10], which has been trained to combine the similarity values obtained from the five models. The final similarity score is provided as the LWN output. To further refine this score, we used the same pipeline to compute the similarity scores for the TRECVID 2023 AVS queries [3], which we use as a set of background queries. These background similarities are then used to normalize the similarity score of each sentence relative to the back-

Figure 2. The Retrieval Module (RM) of our Known-Item-Search Pipeline.

ground queries, as described in [10]. This normalization process is instrumental as a similarity score refinement procedure while it also mitigates the hubness phenomenon [6], a common challenge in high-dimensional similarity spaces.

Stage 3 – Relevant-Shot List Aggregation

For each of the n shots specified in the query, the retrieval process produces m_n ranked lists, each containing a set of candidate video fragments relevant to the sought shot. To aggregate these results into a single ranked list, we apply the following aggregation procedure: We first identify video shots that appear in all m_n lists ($p = m_n$). If the number of retrieved shots is less than K , we iteratively reduce the minimum required appearances across the lists by one ($p = p - 1$) until we obtain at least K video shots. In each iteration, the selected video shots are ranked based on their average similarity scores across the p lists. Video shots that appear in more ranked lists are ranked higher than those appearing in fewer lists, even if the latter have a higher average similarity score. This ensures that consistently retrieved shots are prioritized.

If the query requests a single shot ($n = 1$), the process results in one final list containing the ranked video shots. If the query requests multiple shots ($n > 1$), we generate n separate lists, each corresponding to a different shot. To identify sequences of shots, we apply the following procedure: We start with the first list ($n = 1$) and select its top-ranked video shots. For each selected shot, we check whether any of its subsequent shots (within a predefined range) appear in the second list ($n = 2$). This process continues iteratively across all n lists, ensuring that only sequences of shots meeting these constraints are retained. By following this approach, we extract coherent sequences of video shots that match the query while preserving their

relative order.

In the QA task, since the QA answers are dependent on the entire retrieved video rather than specific shots, we follow a different aggregation approach. We rank a video by the highest rank that any of its shots achieved across all lists, normalized by how often shots of the same video appear and we calculate a score (rank value) where lower scores are better, as follows:

$$Score_{video} = \frac{maxrank}{number_of_appearances} \quad (1)$$

A video that performs well on many lists is ranked higher than one that gets a single top result. Based on these scores we rank the videos, resulting in a list of K relevant videos.

3.3. Question Answering approach

We address the Question Answering task by first retrieving the top K most relevant videos, as described above, and then iteratively attempting to answer the question for each retrieved video. As a prerequisite, we use an LLM to split the given query Q into two segments: a) Q_{vs} , i.e. the information required for video retrieval and b) Q_{qa} , i.e. the question and the necessary context to answer the question.

$$\{Q_{vs}, Q_{qa}\} = LLM_{preprocess}(Q) \quad (2)$$

In order to be able to process long videos, we implement a keyword-based frame selection mechanism, utilizing a multimodal LLM (Qwen2.5 VL). Specifically, given a question Q_{qa} and video V pair, the frame selection process proceeds in three steps. Firstly, by leveraging the provided shot boundaries for each video, we sample the central

frames, denoted as $F = \{f_i\}$, from each shot. In our experiments, we observe that the central frame is generally representative of the whole shot. Then, we instruct the LLM to generate a comma-separated list of $W = 5$ relevant keywords for answering the given question, based only on the question text.

$$keywords = LLM_{keywords}(Q_{qa}) \quad (3)$$

Finally, we iterate over the sampled frames and we instruct the LLM to filter the relevant frames, based on whether each frame matches any of the relevant keywords.

$$k_f(x) = LLM_{framefilter}(x, keywords) \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{F} = \{f_i \mid f_i \in F \text{ and } k_f(f_i) = Yes\} \quad (5)$$

where \hat{F} is the set of the selected frames. This keyword-based approach enables improved fine-grained filtering, since we can select all the frames that match the question, even if the match is partial.

Following LLoVi [40], in order to be able to handle a large number of frames, we implement a caption-based Video QA pipeline. More specifically, given the selected frames from the previous step, we instruct the multi-modal LLM to provide short descriptions (20 words or less) of the frames, denoted as $C = \{c_i\}$.

$$c_i = LLM_{caption}(f_i) \text{ where } f_i \in \hat{F} \quad (6)$$

Following a similar approach to frame selection, we split the audio track into 30-second segments (i.e., the maximum input length of the audio feature extractor), denoted as $A = \{a_j\}$, and we iteratively instruct an audio-pre-trained LLM (Qwen2 Audio) to determine whether the given audio segment is relevant to the given question:

$$k_a(x) = LLM_{audiofilter}(x, keywords) \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{A} = \{a_j \mid a_j \in A \text{ and } k_a(a_j) = Yes\} \quad (8)$$

where \hat{A} is the set of the selected audio segments. Then, we extract subtitles, denoted as $S = \{s_j\}$, from the selected audio segments:

$$s_j = LLM_{transcribe}(a_j) \text{ where } a_j \in \hat{A} \quad (9)$$

Given the extracted captions and subtitles, we ask a text-only LLM to answer the given question:

$$answer = LLM_{qa}(Q_{qa}, C, S) \quad (10)$$

Finally, given the candidate responses for the top K retrieved videos, we adjust their relative rank with a self-feedback mechanism. Specifically, we leverage a text-only LLM, denoted as $LLM_{feedback}$, to determine whether a given response sufficiently answers the original question. We place the candidate responses that answer the question according to the LLM first, and we order them based on the original video retrieval rankings.

4. Results

4.1. Implementation details

For the first stage of the KIS approach we use Gwen 2.5-7B-Instruct [38] as our LLM. For feature extraction, we utilize five cross-modal network families, each leveraging multiple pre-trained models to achieve robust video-text matching. Specifically, we use the text-image network families: the BLIP-2 [15], BLIP [14], SLIP [23], CLIP [26], and BEIT-3 [30] Vision-Language models. For each network family, the following pre-trained model variants are utilized:

- **BLIP-2:** *itm-coco, itm-pretrain, itm-pretrain_vitL*
- **BLIP:** *base-coco, base_flickr, large_coco, large_flickr*
- **SLIP:** *base, small, large, base_CC12M, base_CC3M*
- **CLIP:** *RN50, RN50x4, RN50x16, RN50x64, RN101, ViT-B-16, ViT-B-32, ViT-L-14*
- **BEIT-3:** *{base, large}_patch_16_384_{coco, flickr30k}*

The Learnable Weighting Network (LWN) used for similarity aggregation comprises an input fully connected (FC) layer with 5 nodes, followed by a hidden FC layer consisting of 32 nodes, and is succeeded by a ReLU activation function. The model is trained using the Adagrad optimizer with a learning rate of $3e-5$ over 17 epochs. Additionally, a gradient clipping value of 2 is applied to enhance training stability. The datasets used for training the LWN are MSR-VTT [37], TGIF [17], ActivityNet [7], and VateX [31].

For Video Question Answering, we use the 4-bit quantized version of Qwen2.5-VL-7B-Instruct [4] as our image and text LLM, and Qwen2-Audio-7B-Instruct [8] as our audio LLM. We retrieve the top $K = 70$ or $K = 30$ videos for each query. We extract $W = 5$ keywords per question. We truncate any prompts that exceed the maximum prompt length.

4.2. Experimental setup

The V3C1 dataset is composed of 7475 Vimeo videos (1.3TB, 1000 h) with Creative Commons licenses and mean duration of 8 min. All videos will have some metadata available e.g., title, keywords, and description in json files. The dataset has been segmented into 1,082,659 short video shots according to the provided master shot boundary files. In addition, we extracted one or more frames per video shots (sampling two frames per second).

We evaluate our methods in the fully-automated track of the IVISE25 challenge, using the official 10 queries on the KIS task and the official 10 questions on the QA task, and the official evaluation metric. The score for each query is calculated as follows: $Score = 1 - \frac{(r-1)}{10}$, where r is the rank of the correct answer and 10 is the total number of possible answers for that task. The overall score is the sum of the scores for all tasks.

Query: Close-up of the hand of an elderly Asian man putting down a green beer bottle on the table. There are a full beer glass, some bowls and a box containing a cognac bottle on the table. The camera moves to the man’s face, before going back to his hands, as he uses chopsticks to put food from one bowl into sauce in another bowl.

Sentences:

1. Close-up of the hand of an elderly Asian man.
2. The man is putting down a green beer bottle on the table.
3. There are a full beer glass, some bowls, and a box containing a cognac bottle on the table.
4. The camera moves to the man’s face.
5. He uses chopsticks to pick up food from one bowl.
6. The man then puts the food into sauce in another bowl.

Final retrieved video shots:

Figure 3. Qualitative results: an example of Known Item Search.

Run	Official results			Corrected results		
	Score	#A	#V	Score	#A	#V
1	3.5	4	8	5.2	6	8
2	1.6	3	4	1.6	3	4

Table 3. Official and updated KIS Results for IVISE 2025. #A denotes the number of correct shots and #V denotes the number of correctly retrieved videos.

4.3. KIS results

For participating in the IVISE25 challenge we submit two runs aiming to examine the effectiveness of the retrieval module.

- *run_1*: The complete proposed KIS pipeline with the utilization of background queries for similarity refinement through normalization.
- *run_2*: The proposed KIS pipeline without the similarity refinement part.

In Tab. 3, we present the official IViSE results of our KIS runs as well as corrected/updated results. Following the submission, we identified a bug in the mapping of shots to their corresponding timestamps; specifically, for a given shot $shot_i$, we incorrectly returned the start and end times of $shot_{i+1}$. This issue impacted cases where the correct

video was retrieved. In Tab. 3 we observe that the utilization of the background queries (*run_1*) significantly improves the retrieval performance by correctly retrieving 8 videos and 4 video shots, compared to 4 videos and 3 shots from *run_2*. This improvement becomes even more pronounced when considering the corrected results, where the successfully retrieved shots in *run_1* increase to 5.2.

In Fig. 3, we present qualitative results for an indicative query. This figure illustrates how our LLM-based approach splits the query into smaller sentences and retrieves video shots corresponding to these sentences. At the bottom of the figure, we show the results of the aggregation step, where the individual retrieved shots are filtered and reordered. We observe that the shots retrieved for each sentence are relevant, but the shot that matches the complete query is not found. In contrast, the final ranked list of shots successfully contains this shot (indicated with a green bounding box).

4.4. QA results

We submit three runs, in order to analyze the effectiveness of our design choices.

- *run_1*: The complete Video QA pipeline with $K = 30$.
- *run_2*: The complete Video QA pipeline with $K = 70$.
- *run_3*: The Video QA pipeline without the final feedback and reordering component.

In Tab. 4, we present the results for our VQA runs. We

Question: A man wearing dark trousers and jacket, a scarf and a horse mask walks down a path. There is a wooden bench on the right, cars and houses in the background, and litter on the path and grass. He shakes his head and puts his hand to the head. The camera follows him as he walks to another wooden bench and sits down. Which writer is quoted at the start of this video?

Captions:

1. A black background with a quote by Balzac: "Our conscience is an infallible ..."

Subtitles:

None

Answer: The writer quoted in the video is Balzac.

Question: A woman is sitting in a chair, playing the accordion and singing a song. She has long light-brown hair and wears a red sweater. She is alternatingly shown singing from several perspectives for several minutes. What language is the song in?

Captions:

1. The text "... " appears in black background, suggesting a title or theme related to ...

Subtitles: (...)

3. a woman playing the accordion ...

4. finalemente la vie que l'histoire

(...)

Answer: The language of the song appears to be French.

Figure 4. Qualitative results: two Video Question Answering examples.

Run	Description	#A	#V	Score
<i>Submitted Runs</i>				
1	Full Run with $K = 30$	3	6	2.4
2	Full Run with $K = 70$	3	5	2.4
3	No Reordering	3	6	1.8
<i>With Oracle Video Retrieval and $W = 10$</i>				
-	Full Run	5	-	-
-	No Audio	3	-	-

Table 4. VQA Results for IVISE 2025. #A denotes the number of correct answers and #V denotes the number of correctly retrieved videos.

observe that checking the top $K = 30$ most relevant retrieval results is sufficient for our task and we do not observe any improvements with a higher K value. Furthermore, we experimentally show that the self-feedback and re-ordering component improves the score of our method, without affecting the number of correct answers.

Finally, we perform a QA ablation study, assuming that the correct videos have been retrieved (i.e., using the ground-truth video retrieval results), to study the effect of audio analysis. We observe that the audio pipeline enables the QA framework to correctly answer additional questions, compared to the vision-only baseline. In this ablation, in contrast to the submitted runs, we do not apply 4-bit quantization and we use a higher number of keywords (allowing

more frames and audio segments to be analyzed).

In Fig. 4 we present qualitative results for our proposed Video QA pipeline. We observe that the framework attempts to identify the relevant frames and audio segments within the retrieved video, and by utilizing the reasoning capabilities of the LLM, it generates an accurate answer.

5. Conclusions

We presented our approach for tackling the Known Item Search and Video Question Answering tasks of the IVISE 2025 challenge. We designed an LLM-based pipeline to segment and transform the provided queries, in order to perform video search. We also designed an audio-visual LLM-based pipeline to process long videos, with a keyframe and audio segment selection component, as well as a self-feedback mechanism to improve the Video QA’s robustness to imperfect retrieval results. The proposed approaches extend the limited existing literature on long-form Video QA, especially in combination with automatically retrieving the video used for answering the query.

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